

Evaluation and tagging of dkNET listed repositories

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Introduction

As part of the effort to help NIDDK-supported researchers comply with the upcoming NIH data sharing policy and the [NIDDK Information Network's \(dkNET\)](#) efforts to support FAIR data in this community, we have undertaken an evaluation of the [repositories listed by dkNET](#). As outlined in [Murphy et al. \(2021\)](#), we developed [a tool](#) to assess repositories against criteria consistent with Open, FAIR, Data Citation and Trust Principles (OFCT). This instrument was applied to the ~80 repositories in the list referenced above. A second instrument was developed that [tagged repositories](#) according to criteria that might influence a researcher's selection of a particular repository. Such criteria included: 1) Type of data; 2) Size limits and costs; 3) Ability to handle PHI; 4) Specific use of a DOI; 5) Ease of data citation.

We are still in the process of performing quality control on the data, as conducting these evaluations is difficult, but we provide here an interim report on our findings.

dkNET Repository Listing

The dkNET Repository Listing was compiled by aggregating data from repository listings from NLM, PLoS and Nature, supplemented by repositories added by NIDDK staff. The majority of these repositories are not NIDDK funded, but they cover the major data types likely generated by NIDDK-supported researchers. Additional repositories will be added over time, particularly as NIH is increasing its repository listings ahead of the new NIH data sharing mandate. As a result of our analysis, we will be removing some of our current listings as they are more knowledge bases than databases. All repositories evaluated were on the site as of June 8, 2022.

Methods

The instruments were developed by the core team of Drs. Martone, Murphy and Bar-Sinai, who have worked together several years on developing decision trees for open and FAIR science. For each question, a set of criteria were developed to aid in consistent evaluation by third parties. For the analysis reported here, all evaluations were conducted by a trained curator, Ms. Edyta Vieth, under the supervision of the core team. More detailed methods can be found in Murphy et al., 2021. Therefore the ratings for closed repositories may not be accurate. After an initial evaluation, the results were inspected by the core team and a second round of evaluation was conducted to review the accuracy of the responses. At this time, no attempt was made to reach out to individual repositories to have them review our answers; rather, we based our evaluations on materials available on the website. We plan on alerting repository owners to our evaluations once they are available on the web so that they can correct any errors. Websites are also fluid, and we are noting that more repositories are paying attention to FAIR, likely in response to the NIH policy, leading some to upgrade their web materials over the last year. Copies of the code books for the two questionnaires are included in the Appendix.

For a detailed explanation of the Policy Model tool, please see [Murphy et al. \(2021\)](#).

In addition to the two questionnaires, we also looked into standards currently supported by the repositories and in use in the literature. For the former, we used the [FAIRsharing catalog](#) supplemented with our own notes in some cases. For the latter, we used dkNET's resource mention pipeline to mine the open access literature and also the Endocrine Society journals for mentions of standards and ontologies listed in dkNET's tool registry.

Note that we did not attempt to get accounts to look inside protected sites housing clinical data, in particular, the NIDDK Central Repository. Our information may therefore not be accurate and mostly reflects information on the website.

Results

A total of 78 repositories were evaluated with the two instruments. The first instrument evaluated general compliance with OFCT principles, while the second instrument was geared towards assessing attributes that would be helpful for selecting a repository. Two of the selection attributes are scientific domain (i.e., area of specialization) and data type, shown in Fig 1 and 2 respectively. Domains and data type labels were modified from the classifications used by dkNET in their Repository Listing.

Figure 1: Pie Chart representing scientific domains represented in dkNET Data Repository Listing. General refers to generalist repositories such as FigShare and Dryad. Not stated refers to scientific repositories specialized for a particular data type that did not declare a specific domain.

Of these repositories, we found five that were HIPAA compliant (3 Structural biology, 1 Neuroscience, 1 General) and 73 that did not handle identified human data.

Number of Repositories

Figure 2: Data types specialization represented in dkNET Data Repository Listing

We have created an interactive tool that allows visualization of each of the repositories within the coordinate space created through answering the two questionnaires. The tool allows one to plot each repository in a coordinate space defined by 2-4 variables. Some examples are given in Fig 3-6 and the interactive tool can be accessed here:

Repository Compliance: <http://mbarsinai.com/viz/scicrunch/scicrunch-repoCompliance/>

Repository Tags: <http://mbarsinai.com/viz/scicrunch/scicrunch-repoTag/>

T

Evaluation against OFCT principles

In general, we found that the majority of repositories had features that were at least partially compatible with Open, FAIR, Data Citation and TRUST principles.

Fig 3: Overall repository ratings for FAIR, Open, Citable and Trustworthy features.

Blue = Lowest ranking (a lot of issues)
Red = Middle ranking (some issues)
Gold = Highest ranking (few or no issues)

Fig 4: Visualization of individual repositories within the FAIR policy space. X = Findable, Y = Accessible, Color = Interoperable (Red = not interoperable, brown = partially interoperable, green = fully interoperable), Size = Reusable (small = not reusable, medium = partially reusable; large = fully reusable). Hovering over the repository abbreviations in the interactive tool shows their full name.

Visualizing the individual repositories within the FAIR policy space shows that different repositories scored better or worse on different principles, that is, there were few repositories that were uniformly high ranked or uniformly low ranked across criteria. In this visualization, Findable and Accessible are represented on the X and Y axis respectively, while Interoperable is represented by color and Reusable by size.

Fig 4 provided an overall assessment of FAIR, while Fig 5-6 look at more specific features of FAIR. For example, Fig 5 shows repositories with respect to the first two Findable principles: 1) persistent identifiers (X axis); 2) Rich metadata (Y axis). It is good that most repositories assign a PID, with only 8 ranked lowest on that attribute. However, a significant number assign an internal identifier (33) rather than a fully compliant external PID (36). By external we mean from an external entity, e.g., DOI, or that they have registered their internal identifiers to identifiers.org so that they are resolvable and can redirect if the location changes. Internal identifiers are viewed as less stable and useful, although through registration with Identifiers.org, they can be made to function as PIDs.

The metadata grades were not as high, with 30 repositories ranked as having minimal metadata, 33 limited and only 14 rich metadata.

Fig 5: Policy space for persistent identifiers (X) and rich metadata level (Y). We use the size (Metadata level) and color (Persistent identifier) dimensions to make it easier to place an individual repository within the correct coordinate.

Fig. 6 places the repositories in the license policy space, ranking them according to whether they have an explicit license, e.g., CC-BY, and if so, whether it is applied to the repository or individual dataset level (Reuse Level Y axis) and whether the license is consistent with open science principles (X axis). Here a large number of repositories did not have any license (49) versus those that assign a license at the Repository Level =13, versus the individual dataset level=15. Of those that did have a license, the majority were considered to be supportive of open science (i.e., minimal restrictions on reuse; adequate:5 good:9 full:14).

Fig 6: Policy space for licenses in general (Y axis) and open licenses in particular (X). We use the color (open licenses) and size attributes (license) additionally for these same features

As shown in Fig 3, Data Citation support has the most repositories with the lowest grade and the most with the highest grade. Fig 7 plots the overall citability score (Citable) against specific attributes measured (citation metadata, machine readable landing page, ORCID association). We note that the generalist repositories generally score the highest for data citation while specialist repositories have less support. Data Citation emerged out of organizations like FORCE11 and RDA, organizations in which those running the major generalist repositories were very involved, but this support has not widely filtered across the biomedical ecosystem. Quite a few repositories have machine-readable landing pages (large circles), which is desirable for importing citation metadata into reference managers, but many do not provide the full metadata needed for a citation. Support for linking an ORCID to a dataset is in general very poor. ORCID allows linking published datasets to one's ORCID profile automatically if the repository supports such a function.

Fig 7: Policy space for data citation with the overall citability score shown on the Y axis, the level of citation metadata on the X axis. The level of support for machine readable landing pages (allows import of citation metadata into reference managers) is represented by the size of the circle (small = lowest support; large = highest support) and the linking to ORCID IDs shown in the color dimension (red = no support; brown = some support; green = full support).

Use of standards across dkNET repositories

As part of dkNET’s FAIR recommendations, we advise that researchers think about where their data are going to end up when planning their experiments. In that way, they will know what data standards and metadata are recommended or required by the repository, and they can implement those recommendations within their data management plans. We thus compiled a list of the standards used by each repository. Our main source of information was the FAIRsharing resource, which has compiled a list of such standards. For the purposes of dkNET and guidance to researchers, we focused on standards that would impact the researcher and not technical standards, e.g., XML, JSON or RDF, implemented by the repository.

The top standards are shown in the table below for use of standards across dkNET listed data repositories is provided in Table 1.

Repository standards	Count
Common Metadata Elements for Cataloging Biomedical Datasets	13
FASTA Sequence Format	10
Gene Ontology	6
OmicsDI XML format	6

Schema.org	6
DataCite Metadata Schema	5
JavaScript Object Notation	5
Short read archive extensible markup language	5
HUPO-PSI Universal Spectrum Identifier	4
Minimum Information about a Microarray Experiment	4
Minimum Information about any (x) Sequence	4
Molecular Interaction Tabular	4
Mosquito Insecticide Resistance Ontology	4
mz Markup Language	4
NCBI Taxonomy	4
Protein Databank Format	4
Binary Alignment Map Format	3
Biological Imaging Methods Ontology	3
Bioschemas Dataset Profile	3
DICOM	3
Dublin Core Metadata Element Set	3
FAANG Metadata Experiment Specification Standard	3
FASTA Sequence and Sequence Quality Format	3
INSD sequence record XML	3
Minimum Information about a Molecular Interaction Experiment	3
Minimum Information about a High Throughput Sequencing Experiment	3
Molecular Interaction Extensible Markup Language	3
Scholarly Link Exchange Metadata Schema	3
The Data Use Ontology	3

Table 1: List of standards used across dkNET listed repositories as extracted from FAIRsharing 6/22.

It was encouraging to see the use of common standards across repositories, with a surprising number implementing the Common Metadata Elements for Cataloging Biomedical Datasets and minimal information standards, particularly in molecular biology. However, just because a standard has been implemented, does not mean that submitters are providing the necessary metadata. We have not yet assessed how much metadata is actually provided; we only measure what can be potentially provided.

Mentions of standards and ontologies in the open access biomedical literature

We also utilized our natural language processing pipelines to look for mentions of standards in the open access biomedical literature. Search included both RRID mentions and resource mentions, although the latter may be less accurate than the RRID data. We compiled lists of [all standards](#) and [ontologies](#) listed in dkNET that have at least one mention in the open access literature. Please note that dkNET only searches the open access subset of PubMed Central with some selected journals from Elsevier and Wiley, so our counts may be under-representative of the total count.

Table 2 provides mentions of standards just in open access NIDDK-related journals. The latter list was compiled by searching journal titles for keywords such as metabolism, endocrine etc. Using this approach, we detected ~130 resource mentions, comprising

Standards detected in DK-related journals	Count
PANTHER Functional Classification	16
Gene Ontology	10
SNOMED-CT	1
GUDMAP	2
Minimum Information About a Microarray Experiment	1
Metabolomics Standard Initiative	1
WHO Guidelines	1
NC-IUPHAR	1
CONSORT	1
PRISMA	6
KEGG	6
RDoC	1
EC Classification	1
IMPRINT	1
STROBE	1
GRACE	1

Conclusions and Recommendations

NIDDK can rely on an ecosystem of specialist and generalist repositories to provide the infrastructure for NIDDK-supported researchers to adhere to the new NIH policy guidelines regarding data management and sharing. In our analysis of standards used across repositories, we are seeing some adoption of core standards and domain-specific standards across similar repositories, which is a good sign. Some of these same standards are also mentioned in the literature, e.g., MIAME, suggesting that they are enjoying some community awareness and uptake, although we suspect that this applies to only a small number of standards. Without a repository and tools to support and enforce their use, compliance will likely be minimal.

dkNET assessed these repositories not just against general aspects of FAIR and open science, but against specific attributes that are associated with being able to find, access and reuse data. For example, we looked whether repositories had documentation, that it was easy to access the data through download or an API, the relevance and richness of their metadata, what constituted provenance, and that they had clear licenses and followed best practices on use of persistent identifiers. In a recent survey of data scientists who attempted to use ostensibly open data during the pandemic, all of these features were cited as reasons why it was difficult to reuse data, suggesting that our instrument is assessing features associated with reusability ([Yehudi et al. 2022](#)).

While biomedical repositories still have a long way to go in adopting many OFCT recommendations and best practices, compared to our initial preliminary analysis of repositories against OFCT conducted two years ago, we are seeing more acknowledgment and implementation of FAIR practices within the repositories listed by dkNET suggesting that FAIR and other principles, e.g., the TRUST principles, are making inroads into the infrastructure community. Data citation is lagging somewhat behind in specialist biomedical repositories.

The next steps are 1) To provide these tools as guidance for self-assessment to those who have or want to create a repository serving NIDDK researchers; 2) To create a repository selection wizard that will use the tags to help researchers select an appropriate repository. The standards work will help us alert researchers to any information or format standards enforced or recommended by the repository so that these can factor into their DMSP.

Appendix

The code books for the Repository Compliance with OFCT principles and for the Repository Tagging are provided

DRAFT

Appendices

Appendix A: Code book for Repository Evaluation against OFCT principles instrument

Appendix B: Code book for Repository Tagging instrument

dkNET-Repository Compliance

Production Date 2022-08-31

Version	1.0.0
Release Date	2020-09-13
Localization	en-US
Authors	<p>Maryann E. Martone <i>University of California, San Diego</i> mmartone@ucsd.edu ORCID: 0000-0002-8406-3871</p> <p>Fiona Murphy <i>University of Reading</i> fiona.murphy@reading.ac.uk ORCID: 0000-0003-1693-1240</p> <p>Michael Bar-Sinai <i>Ben-Gurion University of the Negev</i> michael@codeworth.io ORCID: 0000-0002-0153-8465</p>

Question number, id	Question text	Answers
1 [sc-drc.dg]acc	<p>Does the repository provide access to the data with minimal or no restrictions?</p> <p>How easy is it for users to gain access to the data? Are any impediments in place reasonable given the nature of the data, e.g., authorization for sensitive data. Repositories that make metadata available during the embargo period should not be penalized on this question.</p> <p>Options</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No restriction: Accessible without a log in • Minimal restriction: requiring an account and/or the user to sign data policy agreement would be considered a minimal restriction. • Significant restriction, Authorization required: Requiring that someone obtain authorization ahead of downloading data, as would be the case for sensitive data, for example, even if it is understandable. • Significant but not justified: The repository imposes significant restrictions for accessing datasets. Said restrictions are too strict for possible harm mis-use of the data might cause. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. no restrictions 2. minimal restrictions 3. significant restrictions 4. significant but not justified restrictions

2 [sc-drc.dg]reuse

Are you free to reuse the data with no or minimal restrictions?

1. yes
2. somewhat
3. no

Many repositories that claim to be open are only open for humans to read, *not for machine-based access or for re-use*. So it is important to check before depositing the data that it is free to re-use according to the definition of the Commons.

Data should be stored in a non-proprietary format, that is, a format that is published and free for re-use by anyone, such as CSV. In contrast, proprietary formats can only be read by certain commercial software. As the goal of publishing data in a repository is for openness and re-use, data reliant on propriety software is by definition non-commons compliant. Adapted from [Wikipedia](#)

Consider the type of data and whether the access mechanism places undue restraints on the ability to re-use the data. Also, consider the license that specifies 3rd party rights: does it allow the data to be re-used and -shared as part of a new product?

Ideally, the repository should have a clear statement about acceptable file format characteristics. In the absence of such a policy, a check can be made to ascertain which formats are available. If there are both open and closed examples they are coded as "Yes with proprietary formats". If individual data sets are offered under multiple licenses, this can complicate the re-use process further.

Options

- **Yes:** Permissive license or data use terms including the right to re-distribute products arising from the data; open and well supported format
- **Somewhat:** Yes with proprietary formats, or with multiple licenses that require users to navigate the terms separately for each data set. A proprietary format that is still well used and has multiple tools that can read it, such as *xls*, is better than a custom format that is not well supported
- **No:** A proprietary format that is difficult to read without the required software. Inability to distribute data products so that others may build on them. Terms of use are unclear.

3 [sc-drc.dg]lic-clr

Does the repository provide a clear license for reuse of the data?

1. dataset level
2. repository level
3. no license

Ideally, a metadata field **License=** or an easy to find statement on the web page stating the license under which data are released. The license should also ideally be one in common use where the usage rights are clearly stated and uncomplicated.

Options

- **Dataset Level:** Clear license and assigned at the level of individual data sets as part of the metadata
- **Repository Level:** Clear license provided at the level of the repository, e.g., all data are released under a CC-BY license
- **No license**

4 [sc-drc.dg]lic-cc

Are the data covered by a commons-compliant license?

1. best
2. good
3. somewhat open
4. closed

FAIR requires a clear license but it is mute about the level of openness; the Commons requires that the data be as open as possible; closed as necessary. Is the license used consistent with that?

In this question, we use the definition for "Open" from [<https://opendefinition.org/licenses/>](the Open Definition).

These licenses conform to the Open Definition but not to Re-Use

Options

- **best:** all content covered by an open license
- **good:** Some content covered by an open license.
- **somewhat open:** All content covered by a somewhat open license
- **closed:** All content covered by closed license

5 [sc-drc.dg]plat

Does the repository platform make it easy to work with (e.g. download/re-use) the data?

1. yes
2. no

Most repositories provide data for download, but with very large data sets, download can be a significant impediment for reuse. In such a case, a cloud platform may make it easier for researchers to actually reuse the data.

6 [sc-drc.dg]ru-doc

Does the repository require or support documentation that aids in proper (re)-use of the data?

1. best
2. good
3. adequate
4. worst

Vignettes or help that are designed not just for use of the repository, but that helps users understand the types of questions that can be answered by using the data and tools. May be at the repository level for homogeneous data or at the data set level for heterogeneous data. Repositories are expected to have basic help materials and tutorials. We are asking for a level above that to fully achieve FAIR. not just how to perform certain functions but why you can use the resource to answer certain types of questions.

Options

- **best:** Basic tutorials/help + accompanied by use cases or user stories at the repository level and data set level if appropriate
- **good:** Basic tutorials + encouragement and ability to add use cases even if not enforced
- **adequate:** Tutorials but no use cases
- **worst:** Inadequate tutorials + no use cases and no mention of them.

7 [sc-drc.dg]sch-ui

Does the repository provide a search facility for the data and metadata?

1. yes
2. no

Human focused: On-line repositories should provide a means to search available data either through keyword or structured search.

8 [sc-drc.dg]pid-g

Does the repository assign globally unique and persistent identifiers (PIDs)?

1. yes
2. no

A globally unique and persistent identifier is one of the key pillars of FAIR data. If a data set can't be found reliably, i.e., it does not have a stable address that is machine-readable, then it can't be accessible, interoperable or reusable to anyone else. A repository should assign a globally unique and resolvable identifier, e.g., a DOI, to a data set. Many data repositories assign locally unique identifiers, e.g., accession numbers like 5639. These can be turned into globally unique identifiers, e.g., by adding a URL prefix. The repository should also ensure that the identifier is persistent—that is, it is never re-assigned to another entity, even if the underlying data are removed, and the repository must stand behind its resolution, ensuring that the identifier reliably resolves to the data, even if the data move location. For a more detailed description of identifiers, see [The FAIR Principles Explained](#) by the Dutch Techcenter for Life Sciences.

Answer is "Yes" if this is the default option, i.e., an externally linked and registered PID, e.g., a DOI, Handle, ARK. Sometimes Accession numbers are offered as standard. These can be easily upgraded to PIDs through the Compact Identifiers functionality (e.g. by registering them at identifiers.org) but unless this is specified on the website, the response is "No".

9 [sc-drc.dg]orcid

Does the repository allow you to associate your ORCID ID with a dataset?

1. required
2. supported
3. none

Data sets are scholarly works and should be credited as such. The use of ORCID streamlines this process.

Options:

- **Required:** Required and exports relationship to ORCID
- **Supported:** Recommended but not required
- **None:** No use of ORCID

10 [sc-drc.dg]md-level

Does the repository support the addition of rich metadata to promote search and reuse of data?

1. rich
2. limited
3. minimal

We are interpreting rich metadata to include the basic descriptive information about the data set, i.e., those fields recommended by the DCIP, with the addition of critical biomedical metadata, e.g., organism studied, disease condition, technique. dkNET has a recommended set of [rich metadata](#). These data provide an overall context for understanding what the data set is about, but don't necessarily delve into particulars.

Options

- **Rich:** the majority of DCIP fields + biomedical extensions according to dkNET or Bio Schema
- **Limited:** Has some structured metadata but room for improvement
- **Minimal:** Minimal descriptive information

11 [sc-drc.dg]md-prv

Are the (meta)data associated with detailed provenance?

1. best
2. good
3. worst

Is the appropriate provenance provided, e.g., if they use the Gene Ontology term do we know it's from gene ontology? In biomedicine, making sure that the relationship between subjects and specimens and data is explicit is extremely important. RRIDs should be used to make sure that all data sets that use the same strain or sample can be found and combined.

Some aspects to look at:

- Does the repository provide originating information for the data set? Lab, PI, Institution.
- Do they provide a contact person? Does the contact person provide an ORCID?
- Do they use contributor roles so that we know who performed various actions?
- Do they provide an originating publication if applicable?
- Do they provide clear dates for submission and modification?
- Do they have a clear versioning policy?
- If they use external identifiers, are they accessible by their PIDs?
- Do they make provenance of any externally imported or referenced data explicit in the (meta)data?

Options

- **best:** Clear provenance where required + machine readable tag; clear versioning policy and old versions can be accessed
- **good:** Some good things, e.g., clear provenance provided in free text
- **worst:** No clear provenance

12 [sc-drc.dg]md-daci

Does the repository provide the required metadata for supporting data citation?

1. full
2. partial
3. no support

The repository should provide the necessary metadata for a full data citation according to the Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles. Authors, Title of data set, Version, Repository, Date published, PID. It should also be set up to enable exporting the citation reference via a reference manager (e.g. JSON, XML, Bibtex).

Options

- **Full support:** The repository contains a metadata field with the full citation(s).
- **Partial Support:** The repository has the required metadata elements but does not provide an easy way to cite the data. Required metadata should include all contributors just like with an article.
- **No Support:** Insufficient metadata for a full citation, e.g., no title or authors.

13 [sc-drc.dg]md-ref

Do the metadata include qualified references to other (meta)data?

1. best
2. good
3. worst

How well specified are the relationships included in the metadata, e.g., applied in the context of publications, does the resource use the DataCite or some other schema/standard that specifies the relationship of an identifier to the data set, e.g., a PubMed ID for a publication that first reported the data set. Should be machine friendly, e.g., ID's for publications rather than free text.

Options

- **best:** The relationship between the data set or element and an identifier that references an external entity is clearly specified, e.g., the people listed and the related publication are clearly specified.
 - Data publication: DOI or PMID
 - Author: ORCID + metadata
 - Contact person: ORCID + appropriate metadata
- **good:** Identifiers provided but no explicit relationships given
 - Publication: Tagged but doesn't specify the relationship of the publication to the data set clearly
 - Creators: Tagged but doesn't specify key roles clearly
- **worst:** Authors and publication are provided in free text

14 [sc-drc.dg]md-lnk

Does the repository support bidirectional linkages between related objects such that a user accessing one object would know that there is a relationship to another object?

1. best
2. good
3. unclear
4. worst

E.g., does the repository provide a linkage between the publication that first described the data and the data set; does the repository maintain bidirectional linkages between versions, if a dataset has multiple parts, each deposited in a different specialist repository, are the linkages clearly specified across all repositories.

Options

- **best:** Repository not only records article provenance, but links that provenance to the PID such that a consumer of this metadata, e.g., DataCite, Crossref, Zenodo (OpenAIRE) or Scholix, can make use of this information
- **good:** originating article is clearly indicated with an appropriate metadata tag (check landing page metadata)
- **unclear:** publication is there but not indicated by a metadata tag, so the relationship between the data set and the publication is not clear (check landing page)
- **worst:** No record of a publication (and no clear statement that there is no publication) (check landing page)

15 [sc-drc.dg]fmt-com

Does the repository enforce or allow the use of community standards for data format or metadata?

1. yes
2. no

A statement by the repository on the standards they follow and their enforcement policy, including curation and/or software validation. The standards should be recognized as a community standard, e.g., in FAIRsharing or through associated publications. If no such statement can be found on the site, then "No"

16 [sc-drc.dg]md-dkn

Does the repository accept metadata that is applicable to the dkNET community disciplines?

1. best
2. good
3. worst

Biomedical repositories, in addition to the basic [Dublin Core](#) or [Schema.org](#) metadata, require certain fields to maximize utility as specified in dkNET's rich metadata specification. In addition, since dkNET is fostering an information network among the centers and data bases funded by NIDDK, we are expecting that they will include relevant connections to other dkNET listed resources.

Options

- **Best:** plurality. Subject level metadata (ages, weights and sex of each subject rather than pooled data).
- **Good:** some basic biomedically relevant metadata
- **Worst:** only generic metadata is supplied

17 [sc-drc.dg]md-psst

Does the repository have a policy that ensures the metadata (landing page) will persist even if the data are no longer available?

1. by policy
2. by evidence
3. no

Is there evidence that metadata persists even when the data are no longer available. Ideally, repositories clearly state their accessioning and de-accessioning policies as per the data citation principles.

Options

- **by policy:** a clear persistence policy
- **by evidence:** evidence that dataset metadata is persisted when its dataset becomes unavailable (e.g., landing page makes it clear that a data set is no longer available)
- **no:** No policy stated and no evidence.

18 [sc-drc.dg]md-FAIR

Do the metadata use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles?

1. enforced
2. allowed
3. minimal

Use of a community ontology, e.g., OBO, or a controlled vocabulary that follows FAIR principles in order to facilitate combining data from one repository with another.

Options

- **enforced:** Required mapping to appropriate FAIR community ontologies widely used in biomedicine and vocabularies where possible and clear documentation
- **allowed:** Allowed use of identifiers in the metadata scheme although not necessarily enforced; use of some identifiers but lack of mapping in some areas where it would be possible
- **minimal:** Minimal or no mapping to appropriate ontologies

19 [sc-drc.dg]land-ctsp

Does the machine-readable landing page support data citation?

1. yes
2. no

Ideally, the above metadata (both descriptive and data citation relevant) should be able to be harvested automatically, e.g., by a citation manager. We check this by:

1. Can you export landing page metadata in JSON or XML
2. Can you import the landing page metadata into a reference manager tool like Mendeley or Paperpile
3. If you look at the page source, do you see recognizable elements from [Dublin Core](#) or [Schema.org](#) in the markup metatags (Should be in the html head part).

20 [sc-drc.dg]md-cs

Does the repository use a recognized community standard for representing basic metadata?

1. yes
2. no

There are good schemas now available for general purpose data set metadata, e.g., DataCite schema, Dublin Core, schema.org. When a recognized schema is used, it promotes interoperability among data repositories and helps with data set search. Does the repository have supporting software and tools to enforce and take advantage of this standard, e.g., a validator.

Options

- **Yes:** When a recognized schema is mentioned.
- **No:** Otherwise.

21 [sc-drc.dg]acc-api

Can the (meta)data be accessed via a standards compliant API?

1. yes
2. no

The repository provides documentation on how to programmatically access their content and that this method uses a well recognized and used method for access, e.g., RESTful services.

22 [sc-drc.dg]md-vcb

Do the metadata use a formal accessible shared and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation?

1. yes
2. no

The key concept here is "shared". That is, two resources that use the same tags to mean the same thing, can be combined more easily than if they assign custom labels. <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/i1-metadata-use-formal-accessible-shared-broadly-applicable-language-knowledge-representation/> In assessing the repository, consider the hurdles that have to be cleared in order to use the data and metadata, in other words, what does the user have to struggle with before using the data? Check formats, services provided and evaluate whether they conform with the principle.

Resources include [GOFAIR](#):

Humans should be able to exchange and interpret each other's data (so preferably do not use dead languages). But this also applies to computers, meaning that data that should be readable for machines without the need for specialised or ad hoc algorithms, translators, or mappings.

The RDF extensible knowledge representation model is a way to describe and structure datasets. The Dublin Core Schema is an example. Also includes: OWL, JSON LD, OPM (Open Provenance Model) and OntoDM (Ontology for Data Mining), EBI RDF Platform ontologies

Options

- **Yes:** if a formal, accessible language is explicitly listed. Some common formats (including Schema.org/microformats)
- **No:** if no evidence of such a language can be found.

23 [sc-drc.dg]sch-api

Does the repository provide an API-based search of the data and metadata?

1. yes
2. no

Application focused: A remote system can send a query according to a structured API, and the repository will return a list of datasets or research artifacts that match the query criteria.

24 [sc-drc.dg]gov-tsp

Is the governance of the repository transparent?

1. best
2. good
3. worst

In general, the operations of a repository, including the selection of an advisory board, should be transparent.

Evidence of how decisions are made that affect the repository's scope or direction, e.g., Is there an Advisory Board? how are advisory members chosen, what are their terms, how are decisions made on behalf of the repository? Is it one person? Is there a voting system? Do we know who runs the repository?

Options:

- **Best:** Clear and up to date information
- **Good:** Some information but perhaps difficult to find, not exactly clear or up to date
- **Worst:** No information at all

25 [sc-drc.dg]oss

Is the code that runs the data infrastructure covered under an open source license?

1. best
2. good
3. no

From the principles of open infrastructures. If the repository violates the community principles, could the repository be recreated by the community? Some of them are and say so. Some things to look for:

1. Is Code maintained in an open repository?
2. Is the license for the code made clear?
3. Is it an open license?

Options:

- **Best:** Code maintained in an open code repository where it can be forked. The license allows for reuse by 3rd parties.
- **Good:** Code covered under an open license but not maintained in an open repository
- **No:** No evidence of the above

26 [sc-drc.dg]tr-seal

Has the repository been certified by Data Seal of Approval or the Core Trust Seal or equivalent?

1. yes
2. no

These two review processes have merged but either is acceptable and indicates that the repository has undergone an external review for trustworthiness.

Links

- [Data Seal of Approval](#)
- [Core Trust Seal](#)

27 [sc-drc.dg]gov-stk

Is the repository stakeholder governed?

1. full
2. good
3. weak
4. none

Does the repository make it clear how the community participates in the decision making process for the repository.

Should have a listing of the board and evidence that they meet regularly, e.g. minutes, reports, etc.

We adapt here some of the principles for open infrastructures laid out by Bilder G, Lin J, Neylon C (2015) [Principles for Open Scholarly Infrastructure](#). One of the most important is that the repository is stakeholder governed.

Options:

- **Full:** Repository is governed by the research community through a clear governance process
- **Good:** Repository is run by an individual or company but has a strong scientific advisory board that has power to influence decisions.
- **Weak:** Clearly run by NIH/researchers for researchers but not really governed as a community resource
- **None:** Unclear or no accountability to the scientific community, and no means of input

28 [sc-drc.dg]land-api

Does the repository provide a machine-readable landing page?

1. yes
2. no

Ideally, the citation metadata (both descriptive and data citation relevant) should be able to be harvested automatically, e.g., by a citation manager. We check this by:

1. Can you import the landing page metadata into a reference manager tool like Mendeley or Paperpile
2. If you look at the page source, do you see recognizable elements from Dublin Core or Schema.org in the mark up metatags (Should be in the html head part).

More on implementations of machine-readable metadata on dataset landing pages, see M. Fenner et al. *A data citation roadmap for scholarly data repositories*, Scientific Data, 2019. doi.org/10.1038/s41597-019-0031-8.

29 [sc-drc.dg]land-pg

Does the PID or other dataset identifier resolve to a landing page that describes the data?

1. yes
2. no

Both the [FAIR principles](#) and the [Data citation principles](#) require that metadata persist, even if the data they describe are no longer available. FAIR also requires that the access rights to the data be both machine-readable and human understandable. Having the persistent identifier resolve to this page rather than to the data themselves ensures that a stable reference is provided even if the data are removed. The descriptive metadata should also include the necessary information for citing the data set (see Fenner M, Crosas M, Grethe J, Kennedy D, Hermjakob H, Rocca-Serra P, Berjon R, Karcher S, Martone M, Clark T (2016) A Data Citation Roadmap for Scholarly Data Repositories. bioRxiv Dec. 28, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1101/097196>)

We are interpreting this as a stable landing page that contains metadata about the data set that uses the identifier for the data set in the URL. [Cool URI's don't change](#).

30 [sc-drc.dg]md-pid

Does the metadata clearly and explicitly include identifiers of the data it describes?

1. all
2. some
3. none

Should have a metadata field = data set identifier or equivalent that points to the PID or other identifier if no PID Sometimes it is useful to check the API services if documented about what they provide

- *all* All study IDs are included in the metadata
- *some* Some study IDs are included, e.g., accession number but not DOI
- *none* No IDs

31 [sc-drc.dg]pid-1

Does the repository assign, or the contributor provide, a locally unique identifier to the data set or the data contribution?

1. yes
2. no

Examples include an accession number, a UUID, or some other convention.

Note: The use of a title or free text as the unique string is not considered compliant.

End of dkNET-Repository Compliance questionnaire

Data Repository Tagging

Tag a data repository using aspects related to NIH's 2023 data policy

Production Date 2022-08-31

Version	0.3
Release Date	2022-01-24
Localization	en_US
Authors	<p>Maryann E. Martone <i>University of California, San Diego</i> mmartone@ucsd.edu ORCID: 0000-0002-8406-3871</p> <p>Fiona Murphy <i>MoreBrains Cooperative</i> fiona@morebrains.coop ORCID: 0000-0003-1693-1240</p> <p>Michael Bar-Sinai <i>Ben-Gurion University of the Negev / Associate of IQSS @ Harvard University</i> michael@codeworth.io ORCID: 0000-0002-0153-8465</p>

Question number, id	Question text	Answers
1 [decision-graph.dg]qApplication	<h3>Does the repository require depositors to go through an application process prior to depositing datasets?</h3>	1. yes 2. no
2 [decision-graph.dg]qSize	<h3>Does the repository impose size limits?</h3> <p>Some repositories place limits on the size of data that can be deposited. These limits may involve:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> absolute limits, i.e., they will accept no dataset above a certain size; relative limits, e.g., data above a certain size is subject to approval or perhaps additional costs; submission limits, e.g., data above a certain size requires special arrangements for submission. <h4>Terms</h4> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>contact</i>: Contact the repository management for depositing large datasets. 	1. no 2. contact 3. yes
	<h4>Notes</h4> <p>Note any limits in the notes field</p>	

3 [decision-graph.dg]qCost

1. no
2. sometimes
3. always

Does depositing data involve costs to the depositor?

Sometimes there are conditions under which the depositor has to pay.

Notes

Please add those conditions in the notes field.

4 [decision-graph.dg]qVersioning

1. yes
2. no

Does the repository support versioning?

Check whether there's a version number in the metadata, check policy for information, if they handle it as a new data submission then the answer is 'no' unless there's something clearly about the relationship between the different versions.

5 [decision-graph.dg]qPhi

1. yes
2. no

Can the repository store data containing PHI or any other sensitive information?

The repository needs to have an explicit statement that they're able to handle identified human subject data or other sensitive information that cannot be made public. Generally, the repository will have documentation about access requirements, e.g., applying to a data access committee to receive permission to use the data.

Terms

- *PHI*: Protected Health Information. See also [What Health Information Is Protected by the Privacy Rule?](#)

6 [decision-graph.dg]qHIPAA

1. yes
2. no

Is the repository HIPAA compliant?

If it allows human subject data to be deposited, is the repository compliant with US [HIPAA](#)? This is generally in the area of de-identification.

7 [decision-graph.dg]qDomain

1. yes
2. no

Does the repository focus on a specific domain?

Is there a specific biomedical discipline or subdiscipline this repository is serving such that if you're not working within the discipline you would not be depositing data. E.g. AMPT2D.

Note that **domain** is different from **data type** (e.g. genomics).

8 [decision-graph.dg]qDomainList

What is the repository's specific domain?

Select the domain. If it isn't in our list, select 'Other'.

Notes

Please note the domain name in the notes field.

1. Addiction and HIV
2. Cancer
3. Chemistry, chemical biology and biochemistry
4. Diabetes, Digestive and Kidney Diseases
5. Enzymology
6. Fly genetics
7. Immunology
8. Influenza
9. Metabolomics
10. Microbiome
11. Mouse genetics
12. Neuroscience
13. Physiology
14. Structural biology
15. Zebrafish genetics
16. General

9 [decision-graph.dg]qDataType

1. yes
2. no

Does the repository store a single data type?

The repository is primarily built around a single type of data, e.g. imaging data although it may allow multiple types of imaging data. The repository also may allow supporting information that is of another data type.

10 [decision-graph.dg]qDataTypeList

Is this repository specialized for a particular type of data?

1. Clinical trial
2. Crystallography
3. Cytometry
4. Electron microscopy
5. GWAS
6. Genomic
7. Genotype-Phenotype
8. Imaging
9. Interaction/pathways
10. NMR Spectroscopy
11. Neuron reconstruction
12. Neuronal structure
13. Protein structure
14. Proteomic
15. Sequence

11 [decision-graph.dg]qContact

1. yes
2. no

Does the repository supply a contact person?

12 [decision-graph.dg]qFundingSource

1. no
2. yes, any NIH source
3. yes, any NIH institute
4. yes, NIDDK source only

Does the repository require data to come from an NIH funded project?

Terms

- *NIH*: US National Institutes of Health

13 [decision-graph.dg]qPublished

1. yes
2. no

Does the repository require datasets to support a published paper?

If there is no explicit statement that claims this, then we say no.

14 [decision-graph.dg]qCitationMetadata

1. no
2. yes - very limited
3. yes

Does the repository make it easy to cite data?

For example, the repository provides a formatted data citation with each dataset.

Terms

- *limited*: The repository presents formatted data citation that users can cut and paste
- *yes*: The repository can export Bibtext, or allows datasets to be imported into reference managers.

15 [decision-graph.dg]qPID

1. no
2. supports but does not generate
3. supports and generates

Does the repository support PIDs?

If using accession numbers, check in [Identifiers.org](https://identifiers.org) whether the repository has their prefix registered.

Terms

- *PID*: Persistent Identifier - a string or a number that uniquely identifies a dataset indefinitely.
- *Supports but does not generate*: The data repository has a specific field for storing a PID. However, the repository will not create a PID on its own; data depositors must supply one on themselves.

16 [decision-graph.dg]qDOI

1. yes
2. no

Does the repository support DOI?

How to tell: Do the public datasets have a DOI? Sometimes a repository will generate a DOI on request so, may need to look into the documentation.

Terms

- *DOI*: Digital Object Identifier. See doi.org.

Notes

Add any information on the granularity of the DOI in the Notes Field, e.g., assigns DOIs at the study level but not at the individual experiment level.

End of Data Repository Tagging questionnaire